

www.arseam.com

**International Journal of
Advances in Engineering
& Scientific Research**

Become a Pro

**International Journal
of Advances in
Engineering &
Scientific Research
(IJAESR)**

ISSN: 2349 –3607 (Online)
ISSN: 2349 –4824 (Print)

Available online at:
<http://www.arseam.com/content/volume-1-issue-4-aug-2014>

Email: editor@arseam.com

Instructions for authors and
subscription information:
<http://www.arseam.com/>

a Academic Research
ARSEAM IN SCIENCE, ENGINEERING, ART & MANAGEMENT

USE OF MICROCLIMATE IN PASSIVE COOLING

Avinash Devadwal¹, P.B.L. Chaurasia² and Mr.P.N.Mathur³

1. M.Tech Research Scholar

2. Dean Engg. Suresh Gyan Vihar University, Jaipur

3. HOD of civil department, Suresh Gyan Vihar University, Jaipur

Centre Of Excellence, Solar Energy Research & Utilization,
Suresh Gyan Vihar University, Jaipur

Abstract

Microclimate refers to a climate of a small region . As the name suggests , Micro means small and the term signifies the effect of climate on a smaller regions due to surroundings of that area . Microclimate effects the enviornment . For example, Concrete and masonry absorbs heat from sun and slowly radiate which increases the temperature. This is called urban heat island effect. Now having Non radiating shading devices like trees and plants nearby can help in regulating the temperature.

Factors affecting microclimate

There are certain factors which plays an important role in microclimate.

1. Orientation of building
2. Location of neighboring objects
3. Surrounding landscape

The micro climate can also determine the shape of the building and how it sits on the site and the locations of your rooms within the building.

An ideal site for the designing an energy efficient home would be one that has full solar access and protection from the harsh elements of nature.

Zones

The zoning and orientation of the building can have a strong impact on the energy consumption pattern.

Shape can have a strong influence on energy consumption performances.

- Solar gain
- Savings on energy consumption
- Integration of technology
- Pressure Distribution
- Wind patterns

For instance, it can determine the amount of solar radiation falling onto the external surface area. This in return can increase savings on energy, for example, heating and lighting. The form of the building should take into account the integration of technology, to maximise efficiency. Other affected factors are pressure distribution throughout the building and wind patterns etc. Microclimatic conditions depend on such factors as temperature, humidity, wind and turbulence, dew, frost, heat balance, and evaporation. The effect of soil type on microclimates is considerable. Sandy soils and other coarse, loose, and dry soils, for example, are subject to high maximum and low minimum surface temperatures. The surface reflection characteristics of soils are also important; soils of lighter colour reflect more and respond less to daily heating. Another feature of the microclimate is the ability of the soil to absorb and retain moisture, which depends on the composition of the soil and its use. Vegetation is also integral as it controls the flux of water vapour into the air through transpiration. In addition, vegetation can insulate the soil below and reduce temperature variability. Sites of exposed soil then exhibit the greatest temperature variability.

Topography can affect the vertical path of air in a locale and, therefore, the relative humidity and air circulation. For example, air ascending a mountain undergoes a decrease in pressure and often releases moisture in the form of rain or snow. As the air proceeds down the leeward side of the mountain, it is compressed and heated, thus promoting drier, hotter conditions there. An undulating landscape can also produce microclimatic variety through the air motions produced by differences in density.

The microclimates of a region are defined by the moisture, temperature, and winds of the atmosphere near the ground, the vegetation, soil, and the latitude, elevation, and season. Weather is also influenced by microclimatic conditions. Wet ground, for example, promotes evaporation and increases atmospheric humidity. The drying of bare soil, on the other hand, creates a surface crust that inhibits ground moisture from diffusing upward, which promotes the persistence of the dry atmosphere. Microclimates control evaporation and transpiration from surfaces and influence precipitation, and so are important to the hydrologic cycle—*i.e.*, the processes involved in the circulation of the Earth's waters.

Use of shade trees, shrubs and vines can provide protection from solar radiation in summer. Careful planting of trees for wind channelling can provide efficient ventilation and circulation of summer breezes in addition to creating attractive spaces for outdoor activity. However some care should be taken in the choice and placement of vegetation on or near the building to avoid structural damage.

Grass and other ground cover planting can also influence the microclimate, keeping the ground temperature lower than most hard surfaces as a result of evapotranspiration and their ability to reduce the effect of solar radiation. This happens due to the shading provided by the grass which prevents radiation from reaching the ground resulting in a difference between asphalt and lawn being as much as 25 degrees F (figures taken from Climatic design, Energy efficient building principles & practises/ Donald Watson and Kenneth Labs).

Windbreaks can enhance air pressure difference around buildings and improve cross ventilation. Hedging, for example, can allow a gentle breeze to filter through the foliage, while a masonry windbreak can create a calm, sheltered zone behind it. Gaps in windbreaks, openings between buildings or openings between the ground and canopy of trees can create wind channels, increasing wind speeds by about 20%.

Water can also be used effectively for cooling of internal as well as surrounding environment. Ponds, streams, fountains, sprays and cascades can be used where water is available in summer. These are particularly effective in dry conditions where relative humidity levels are low.

References :

- [1] www.c2es.org/technology/factsheet/BuildingEnvelope
- [2] http://www.ijetae.com/files/Volume4Issue4/IJETAE_0414_131.pdf
- [3] Erens PJ, Dreyer AA. Modeling of indirect evaporative Coolers Int J Heat Mass Tran 1993; 36:17-26
- [4] http://mospi.nic.in/research_studies_post_clearance.htm
- [5] http://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007%2F978-3-540-76694-0_207#page-1,2
- [6] <http://www.silascience.com/articles/29112012150107.pdf>
- [7] http://www.jtp.co.uk/public/uploads/pdfs/120813_jtp_bioclimatic_design.pdf
- [8] 7. J.P. Gupta and P.B.L.Chaurasia, Potential of nocturnal cooling in arid conditions at Jodhpur, Proc. of National Solar Energy Convention, Bangalore, India, 4(1981)5.019-5.022.
- [9] J.P. Gupta and P.B.L.Chaurasia, Comparative potential of nocturnal cooling in evening and morning, Proc. National Solar Energy Convention, New-Delhi, India, 10 (1982)10.004-.006.